

Simulation of an Autonomous Voice Controlled Robotic Arm using ROS2 and Plansys2

Dr. Ambika GN
*BMS Institute of Technology and
Mangement*
Bangalore, INDIA
bhn

Sai Harshit B
*BMS Institute of Technology and
Mangement*
Bangalore, INDIA
1by20cs162@bmsit.in

Vigneshwaran PS
*BMS Institute of Technology and
Mangement*
Bangalore, INDIA
1by20cs215@bmsit.in

Chaitra Sri Naidu Chenaboina
*BMS Institute of Technology and
Mangement*
Bangalore, INDIA
1by20cs044@bmsit.in

S Guru Prasad
*BMS Institute of Technology and
Mangement*
Bangalore, INDIA
1by20cs0154@bmsit.in

Abstract— The Autonomous Voice-Controlled Arm Robot (A.V.C.A.R.) project explores the development of a robotic arm capable of executing tasks from natural language voice commands. Implemented in simulation using ROS2 and Plansys2, the system integrates speech recognition, object detection, task planning, and motion planning to enable autonomous manipulation within a workspace. The approach provides an intuitive voice-based interface that improves accessibility for individuals with limited mobility and reduces reliance on manual control. Results from Gazebo simulation demonstrate reliable object recognition, multi-step plan generation, and successful pick-and-place operations. This work highlights the feasibility of combining voice interaction with AI-driven planning to create adaptable assistive robotic systems, with future extensions toward hardware implementation.

Keywords— *Assistive robotics, ROS2, Plansys2, Voice-controlled robotic arm, Human-robot interaction, Simulation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in robotics and artificial intelligence are creating new opportunities to support elderly and disabled individuals, and those without regular caregivers. This project — the *Autonomous Voice-Controlled Arm Robot (A.V.C.A.R.)* — addresses one such opportunity by enabling natural-language voice commands to drive autonomous manipulation in a simulated domestic workspace.

A.V.C.A.R. is implemented on the Robot Operating System 2 (ROS2) and uses the Plansys2 PDDL-based planning framework for high-level reasoning. The system integrates four core capabilities: (1) **speech recognition** to convert spoken commands into text and goal statements, (2) **perception** using computer vision for object detection, (3) **task planning** via Plansys2 to generate ordered action sequences from goals, and (4) **motion planning** with MoveIt2 to produce executable trajectories for the arm. ROS2 provides the modular middleware needed for these components to interoperate through topics, services, and actions.

This paper presents the design, implementation, and simulation-based validation of A.V.C.A.R. in Gazebo. We demonstrate how parsed voice commands are translated into PDDL goals, how the planner produces multi-step plans, and how MoveIt2 executes those plans in simulation.

By focusing on an end-to-end software pipeline rather than hardware, this work provides a proof-of-concept for integrating modern speech recognition, vision-based perception, symbolic planning, and motion control within a ROS2 framework. The results highlight the system's potential to increase accessibility and autonomy for users with limited mobility and to serve as a foundation for future hardware deployment and extended capabilities.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The field of assistive robotics has witnessed significant advancements in recent years, driven by the convergence of robotics and artificial intelligence (AI). This section delves into relevant research efforts that have paved the way for the development of the Autonomous Voice Controlled Arm Robot (A.V.C.A.R.) project.

A. Planning Systems for Robotics

Martin et al. [1] introduced Plansys2, a PDDL-based planning system framework specifically designed for ROS2. This framework serves as the foundation for the A.V.C.A.R. project's planning capabilities, enabling the robotic arm to reason and plan its actions autonomously.

B. Object Manipulation in Robotic Environments

Militaru et al. [2] presented a study on object handling in cluttered environments using a mobile manipulator. Their work demonstrates the feasibility of operating robotic arms in complex settings, which aligns with the A.V.C.A.R. project's goal of assisting individuals in their home environments.

C. Computer Vision and Deep Learning for Robotic Control

Melo et al. [3] explored the integration of deep learning with computer vision for robotic arm control. Their work highlights the potential of utilizing deep learning algorithms for object recognition and manipulation tasks, which are crucial functionalities within the A.V.C.A.R. project.

D. Voice-Controlled Robotic Systems

Zhang et al. [4] presented the development of a voice-controlled dual-arm robot operating in hazardous environments. This work showcases the capabilities of voice-based control for robotic manipulation, a key feature implemented in the A.V.C.A.R. project.

E. Vision-Based Robot Manipulation for Assistive Applications
Megalingam et al. [5] investigated the integration of vision-based robot manipulation using ROS for assistive applications. Their research aligns with the A.V.C.A.R project's objective of providing assistive functionalities through robotic manipulation.

F. ROS-based Voice-Controlled Robotic Arm for Medical Waste Segregation

Tasnim et al. [6] presented a ROS-based voice-controlled robotic arm for medical waste segregation using the YOLOv3 object detection algorithm. This work demonstrates the potential of voice control and object recognition in specific assistive applications, further supporting the A.V.C.A.R project's goals.

G. Voice-Controlled Robotic Arm for Assistive Applications

Salim et al. [7] proposed a lightweight robotic arm controlled through voice commands using Arduino microcontrollers and speech recognition modules. Their work highlights how natural language interaction can provide independence to individuals with motor impairments by enabling them to operate robotic arms without manual control. This approach supports the A.V.C.A.R project's emphasis on effortless and user-friendly human-robot interaction.

H. User-Centered Design for Wheelchair-Mounted Robotic Arms

Jia et al. [8] investigated user expectations and interface requirements for voice-controlled, wheelchair-mounted robotic arms (WMRAs). Through semi-structured interviews with wheelchair users, they identified key needs such as safety feedback, versatile gripping capabilities, and transparency in system performance. Their findings stress the importance of aligning robotic functionality with user trust and preferences, aligning with the A.V.C.A.R project's focus on user-centred assistive technologies.

I. Voice-Controlled Robotic Assistant with Arduino Uno

Kadam et al. [9] developed a voice-controlled robotic assistant that integrates Arduino Uno, Bluetooth communication, and ultrasonic sensors to execute tasks through natural language commands. Their system supports both **virtual assistance** (answering user queries) and **physical assistance** (pick-and-place operations), thereby serving as an aid for students, elderly individuals, and persons with disabilities. This dual-mode interaction demonstrates how robotic assistants can provide multifunctional support, complementing the A.V.C.A.R project's emphasis on versatility and accessibility in assistive robotics.

J. Robotic Arm Vehicle with Voice Recognition for Accessibility

Nannda et al. [10] introduced a robotic arm vehicle designed to aid physically challenged individuals through voice recognition. The system integrates a robotic vehicle platform with a pick-and-place arm controlled via predefined voice commands. Their experiments demonstrated efficiency improvements in grasping accuracy and task completion time compared to earlier systems, while

also incorporating AI and IoT for enhanced adaptability in real-world environments. This work supports the A.V.C.A.R project's mission of combining mobility, manipulation, and natural interaction to improve user independence.

K. Voice-Controlled 6-DOF Arm in Assisted Home Environments

Abhiram and Udupa [11] presented a voice-controlled mobile robot equipped with a six-degree-of-freedom (6-DOF) robotic arm for pick-and-place tasks in assisted living settings. Their system integrates **ROS, MoveIt motion planning, and A*** algorithms for efficient navigation and manipulation, while also employing Intel RealSense depth cameras for object recognition. The robot was further enhanced with **Alexa-based voice control**, enabling intuitive user interaction and remote task execution. This research highlights the importance of combining advanced motion planning with natural language interfaces, which directly supports the A.V.C.A.R project's objective of creating adaptable assistive robotic systems for home environments.

L. Task Extension with Voice Control Using Dynamical Movement Primitives

Zhang et al. [12] proposed a method to extend robotic task generalization by combining **Dynamical Movement Primitives (DMPs)** with voice commands. Complex tasks were segmented into simpler sub-trajectories, which could then be recombined and executed under user voice control. Using a Baxter robot, the experiments showed that this approach significantly improved the adaptability of robots to new tasks without retraining. This work informs the A.V.C.A.R project's long-term vision of integrating learning-based motion generation with natural language control for greater flexibility.

M. Voice-Controlled Robotic Arm for Hazardous Environments

Kanash et al. [13] designed a robotic arm system capable of operating in hazardous environments such as oil fields and polluted areas. Their prototype, built using an Arduino controller, NRF wireless sensors, and a trained voice module, enabled the execution of precise manipulation tasks under predefined voice commands. This research demonstrates the value of combining wireless communication with voice control to ensure operator safety in dangerous workspaces, complementing the A.V.C.A.R project's emphasis on robust assistive technologies for real-world deployment.

N. Assistive Robotic Arm with Object Detection Feedback for the Visually Impaired

Minera and George [14] presented a voice-controlled robotic arm system equipped with feedback mechanisms to assist visually impaired individuals. The system integrated Google Speech-to-Text API for voice command processing and YOLOv7-based object recognition to provide contextual awareness. Additional feedback was provided using weight sensors for object verification. This work demonstrates the integration of multimodal feedback with voice-controlled systems, directly supporting the A.V.C.A.R project's aim of providing inclusive assistive solutions.

O. Voice-Controlled Robotic Arm for Material Handling

Saravanan et al. [15] introduced a robotic arm designed for industrial and hazardous settings, controlled wirelessly via Android devices and voice commands. The system employed a microcontroller with Bluetooth communication to perform pick-and-place tasks, supplemented by a camera feed for remote monitoring. Their research underlines the utility of combining mobile platforms with robotic arms for material handling, reflecting the A.V.C.A.R project's focus on practical usability in diverse environments.

P. Wireless Voice-Controlled Robotic Vehicle

Kuriakose et al. [16] developed a wireless robotic vehicle that responds to voice commands transmitted from an Android application via Bluetooth. The system employs Arduino microcontrollers and geared DC motors to enable navigation in multiple directions under natural speech control. Their work highlights the feasibility of low-cost, voice-enabled mobile robotic platforms, aligning with the A.V.C.A.R project's goal of creating affordable and scalable assistive solutions.

Key Takeaways:

The reviewed literature highlights the growing advancements in assistive robotics, particularly in the areas of planning systems, object manipulation, computer vision, voice control, and ROS-based development. These advancements provide a strong foundation for the development of the A.V.C.A.R project, which aims to leverage these technologies to create a user-friendly and intelligent assistive robotic system.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

In the realm of assistive robotics, traditional systems often rely on rudimentary interfaces and limited autonomy, constraining their effectiveness in addressing the diverse needs of vulnerable populations. These conventional systems typically feature simplistic control mechanisms, such as manual joysticks or pre-programmed sequences, which necessitate significant user effort and offer limited adaptability to dynamic environments. Moreover, without the sophisticated planning capabilities afforded by Plansys2, these systems lack the capacity to autonomously devise and execute complex tasks in response to user commands.

One prominent limitation of existing systems is their inability to seamlessly integrate natural language voice commands, which are integral to facilitating intuitive human-robot interaction. Without the advanced linguistic processing capabilities of Plansys2, users are often required to rely on cumbersome interfaces or external devices for communication, impeding their ability to interact fluidly with the robotic system. Additionally, the absence of AI-driven planning hampers the system's adaptability and scalability, making it challenging to extend its functionality beyond predefined tasks. As a result, users may experience frustration and limitations in their ability to leverage assistive robotics to enhance their independence and quality of life.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This research proposes a novel methodology for developing an autonomous voice-controlled robotic arm capable of independent task planning and execution. The Robot Operating System (ROS) serves as the foundational framework, enabling modular development and communication between the core subsystems: Task Planning, Motion Planning & Control, Perception, and Speech Recognition.

Fig 3.1 Level Zero Data Flow Model

Task Planning: Plansys2 leverages the STRIPS algorithm to generate high-level task sequences based on user goals.

Motion Planning & Control: MoveIt2 handles motion planning and trajectory generation. It utilizes the RRT* algorithm for efficient path optimization within the robot's workspace.

Perception: The perception subsystem combines camera input with OpenCV and YOLO for object detection. This information is then converted into predicates suitable for task planning.

Speech Recognition: DeepSpeech or WhisperAI are employed to convert spoken commands into text, which is subsequently parsed into a goal statement for the planning system. Ongoing research focuses on parsing voice commands into PDDL syntax for direct execution.

Fig 3.2 Flowchart of Execution Process

Integration and Communication:

ROS facilitates seamless communication between subsystems through topics, services, and actions. C++ and Python are the primary programming languages, with C++ handling low-level execution and Python managing complex processes like AI and computer vision.

This modular design allows for independent development and integration, making the system adaptable to different robot configurations with minimal modifications.

V. ALGORITHMS USED

Rapidly-exploring Random Tree Star (RRT*):

The Rapidly-exploring Random Tree Star (RRT*) algorithm is an extension of the RRT algorithm that not only explores the configuration space efficiently but also improves path quality over time. It incrementally builds a tree rooted at the start configuration by randomly sampling points and connecting them through feasible paths.

Unlike RRTConnect, which provides suboptimal solutions, RRT* incorporates an optimization step (rewiring) to ensure that as the number of samples increases, the generated path converges to the globally optimal solution.

Pseudocode:

Input: Initial state x_{init} , goal region X_{goal} , number of iterations N

Output: Path from x_{init} to X_{goal} (if found)

```
1: Initialize tree T with root node  $x_{init}$ 
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
3:    $x_{rand} \leftarrow \text{SampleRandomState}()$ 
4:    $x_{nearest} \leftarrow \text{NearestNeighbor}(T, x_{rand})$ 
5:    $x_{new} \leftarrow \text{Steer}(x_{nearest}, x_{rand}, \epsilon)$ 
6:   if  $\text{CollisionFree}(x_{nearest}, x_{new})$  then
7:      $X_{near} \leftarrow \text{Near}(T, x_{new}, r_n)$ 
8:      $x_{min} \leftarrow \text{ChooseParent}(X_{near}, x_{new}, T)$ 
9:      $\text{AddNode}(T, x_{new}, \text{parent} = x_{min})$ 
10:     $\text{Rewire}(T, x_{new}, X_{near})$ 
11:  end if
12: end for
13: return  $\text{ExtractBestPath}(T, X_{goal})$ 
```

Formulae

- **Cost of a path** from the root to a node x :
$$c(x) = \sum \left\| x_{i+1} - x_i \right\|$$

Meaning: This formula defines the **cost of reaching a node x** in the tree from the start configuration.

Each term $\|x_{i+1} - x_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between two consecutive configurations (nodes) along the path.

The summation adds up all these distances, giving the **total path length** (or more generally, the cost if

using weighted metrics).

In robotics, minimizing this cost corresponds to finding the **shortest or least expensive path**.

- **Neighbourhood radius** for rewiring:

$$r_n = \gamma \left(\frac{\log n}{n} \right)^{1/d}$$

Meaning: This formula defines the **radius of the neighbourhood** around a new node within which the algorithm checks for better (lower-cost) connections.

Parameters:

- n : Number of nodes already in the tree.
- d : Dimension of the configuration space (e.g., 2D or 6D for a robotic arm).
- γ : A constant chosen to guarantee optimality.

As n increases, the radius r_n shrinks, ensuring the algorithm refines connections locally rather than rewiring globally. This balance ensures **exploration in the early stages** and **optimization in later stages**.

RRT* has become a standard in motion planning due to its ability to balance exploration with optimization. Its asymptotic optimality makes it particularly suitable for robotic applications where minimizing path length or energy consumption is critical, such as in MoveIt2-based robotic arm planning.

STRIPS Algorithm:

The STRIPS algorithm is a foundational planning method in artificial intelligence, widely used for symbolic reasoning and task planning. It models the environment as a set of logical states and actions that transform these states. Each action is defined by preconditions that must hold before execution and effects that update the state after execution. This structured representation allows STRIPS to generate action sequences (plans) that achieve user-defined goals from an initial state.

Pseudocode:

Input: Initial state S , Goal state G , Set of actions A

Output: Plan $\pi = \langle a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \rangle$

```
1: Open  $\leftarrow \{S\}$ 
2: while Open is not empty do
3:    $s \leftarrow \text{RemoveFirst}(\text{Open})$ 
4:   if  $\text{GoalSatisfied}(s, G)$  then
5:     return  $\text{ExtractPlan}(s)$ 
6:   end if
7:   for each action  $a \in A$  applicable in  $s$  do
8:      $s' \leftarrow \text{ApplyAction}(s, a)$ 
9:     Record predecessor of  $s'$  as  $s$  and action  $a$ 
10:    Insert  $s'$  into Open
11:  end for
```

12: end while
 13: return Failure (no plan found)

Formulae:

- **State transition function:**

$$\gamma(s, a) = (s - \text{Del}(a)) \cup \text{Add}(a)$$

Meaning: This function models how the system's state s changes when an action a is applied.

- $\text{Del}(a)$: The set of facts removed from the state (things that stop being true after the action).
- $\text{Add}(a)$: The set of facts added to the state (new conditions that become true after the action).

Example: If the action is $\text{Pick}(\text{Object})$, then:

- o Delete = {OnTable(Object)}
- o Add = {InHand(Object)}

This formula captures the **before-and-after effect of actions** in symbolic planning.

- **Plan correctness:**

$$\gamma(\gamma(\dots\gamma(s_0, a_1), a_2), \dots, a_n) \models G$$

Meaning: This expression shows that if we start from the **initial state** s_0 and apply the sequence of actions a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n , the resulting state satisfies the **goal conditions G**.

The notation $\models G$ means "entails the goal" (i.e., the final state meets the goal requirements).

This ensures that the **entire sequence of actions (the plan) is valid**.

In robotics, this guarantees that symbolic planning (STRIPS/PlanSys2) achieves the user-defined objective.

STRIPS provides a clear and mathematically rigorous framework for task planning, enabling complex goals to be decomposed into executable actions. Its principles underpin modern planners such as PlanSys2, allowing robots to perform high-level reasoning and execute multi-step tasks in dynamic environments.

VI. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the Autonomous Voice-Controlled Robotic Arm (A.V.C.A.R) system is designed within the Robot Operating System 2 (ROS2), leveraging its capability to modularize and integrate various subsystems seamlessly. A.V.C.A.R comprises distinct subsystems for efficient task execution:

- **Task Planning Subsystem:** This subsystem utilizes Plansys2, a PDDL-based planning framework, to generate action sequences based on user commands and environmental information.

- **Motion Planning and Arm Control Subsystem:** This subsystem employs MoveIt2, a motion planning library, to translate high-level plans into feasible trajectories and control commands for the robotic arm.
- **Camera Perception Subsystem:** This subsystem utilizes computer vision techniques, potentially including object detection algorithms like YOLOv8, to extract environmental information from camera input.
- **Speech Recognition Subsystem:** This subsystem integrates a speech recognition API, such as Whisper, to convert user voice commands into text format for processing by the planning system.

Communication and Integration:

Individual subsystems operate independently within the ROS2 framework, communicating through message passing using nodes and services. Figure 4.1 illustrates the core system logic and communication flow:

Fig 4.1 System Architecture

- **Environment Server:** This node is the Perception module, receiving camera input and extracting environmental information used by both the planning system and the motion planning subsystem (MoveIt2).
- **Goal Server:** This node receives user voice commands through speech recognition and transmits them to the planning system (Plansys2 Node).
- **Plansys2 Node:** This node utilizes the information from the Environment Server and the user command to generate a task plan, including a sequence of actions.
- **Action Nodes:** These nodes provide feedback to the Plansys2 node and send function calls to the MoveIt2 node for execution.
- **MoveIt2 Node:** This node receives the task plan and environmental information to plan the arm's trajectory and motion. The output controls the actual arm movement, visualized through simulation tools like Gazebo or directly on the hardware arm itself.

Additional Subsystems:

- **Gazebo Subsystem:** This subsystem utilizes Gazebo, a 3D robot simulator, to model the robotic arm and simulate its movements in various environments during development and testing.

Fig 4.2 Gazebo Subsystem

Plansys2 Subsystem: This subsystem provides the planning framework (Plansys2) for generating and executing task plans, enabling autonomous decision-making and adaptation within the system.

Fig 4.3 Plansys2 Subsystem

Perception Subsystem: This subsystem focuses on object detection within the robot's environment. Algorithms like YOLOv8, trained on datasets like COCO, can be utilized for this purpose.

Fig 4.4 Perception Subsystem

Speech Recognition Subsystem: This subsystem integrates a speech recognition API, such as Whisper, to convert user voice commands into text for further processing.

ROS2 Humble serves as the middleware framework facilitating inter-subsystem communication. The architecture employs Actions and Services extensively for seamless integration:

- The Environment Service facilitates the transmission of environmental data from the Perception module.
- The Goal Service mediates communication between the Goal Server (Speech Recognition) and Plansys2 nodes, handling user commands.
- Actions connect the Plansys2 and Action Nodes, with each Action node executing a distinct action. Action nodes utilize Services to request execution from the MoveIt2 node.

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the A.V.C.A.R system's design and architecture, including its core subsystems, communication mechanisms, and the role of additional tools like Gazebo and Plansys2. Remember to replace placeholders with actual figure captions and include the figures within the paper according to the specified locations.

VII. RESULT

The Autonomous Voice Controlled Arm Robot (A.V.C.A.R) system demonstrates the integration of voice recognition, perception, planning, and motion control modules within the ROS2 framework. Speech recognition using the SpeechMatics API successfully converted spoken commands into text with high reliability in controlled conditions.

For object perception, the camera was trained on a limited dataset consisting of three household objects: a soda can, a bottle, and a cup. In Gazebo simulations, the object detection subsystem achieved an average recognition accuracy of **80% over 30 runs**.

The planning and execution pipeline, implemented with Plansys2 and MoveIt2, generated task sequences averaging **6–7 steps per user command**. Each step required approximately **20 seconds**, leading to a total execution time of **2–3 minutes per full command sequence**.

Pick-and-place trials validated the motion planning component, with the system consistently completing tasks when objects were correctly detected. Figures 5.1–5.4 illustrate the process from user input to plan generation and task execution.

These results indicate that A.V.C.A.R can reliably process natural language commands, detect predefined objects, and autonomously execute multi-step manipulation tasks in simulated environments. The outcomes also highlight the system's modularity and potential for scaling to additional object categories and more complex tasks.

VIII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We extend heartfelt thanks to Dr. Ambika G N, assistant professor, Department of CSE, BMSIT, our internal guide for her invaluable guidance during the successful completion of our group project. Special appreciation to Dr. Thippeswamy G, HOD, Department of CSE, BMSIT, for creating an enabling environment, and to Dr. Sanjay H A, Principal, BMSIT, for fostering academic excellence. This achievement is a result of their unwavering support. We are grateful for the opportunity to apply the skills gained in future endeavors.

IX. CONCLUSION & FUTURE

In conclusion, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with robotics has propelled the development of sophisticated systems like the Autonomous Voice Controlled Arm Robot (A.V.C.A.R). Currently, A.V.C.A.R demonstrates the capability to process natural language voice commands, detect objects, and execute tasks autonomously. This fusion of AI and robotics has revolutionized the field of assistive robotics, offering a seamless interface for users to interact with robotic systems and enhancing their independence and quality of life.

Looking ahead, the future holds immense potential for advancing the functionality and versatility of A.V.C.A.R. Future plans include the implementation of more complex actions such as handling doors and opening bottles, showcasing the system's adaptability to diverse tasks. Additionally, efforts will be directed towards intelligent grasping techniques, enabling the robotic arm to manipulate objects with precision and dexterity.

Furthermore, the onboard voice recognition system will undergo refinement to enhance accuracy and responsiveness, ensuring seamless interaction between users and the robotic system. Moreover, the integration of multiple arms coordinating with each other will be explored, facilitating collaborative tasks and expanding the range of applications for A.V.C.A.R.

In summary, the ongoing development and integration of AI technologies with robotics hold promise for extending the functionality and capabilities of assistive robotic systems like A.V.C.A.R. By embracing these advancements, we can continue to push the boundaries of human-robot interaction and create more intelligent, adaptable, and user-friendly robotic systems to support and empower individuals in their daily lives.

X. REFERENCES

- [1] F. Martín, J. G. Clavero, V. Matellán and F. J. Rodríguez, "PlanSys2: A Planning System Framework for ROS2," 2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), Prague, Czech Republic, 2021, pp. 9742- 9749, doi: 10.1109/IROS51168.2021.9636544.

Fig 5.1: This image displays the user input command for a specific task.

Fig 5.2: The plan generated based on the user input command is showcased in this image.

Fig 5.3: The image illustrates the successful execution of the pick action as part of the task.

Fig 5.4: This image exhibits the completion of the place action, concluding the task initiated by the user.

- [2] Militaru, Cristian & Mezei, Ady-Daniel & Tamas, Levente. (2016). Object handling in cluttered indoor environment with a mobile manipulator. 1-6. 10.1109/AQTR.2016.7501382.
- [3] R. Melo, T. Pontes de Araújo, A. Andrade Saraiva, J. V. Moura Sousa and N. M. Fonseca Ferreira, "Computer Vision System with Deep Learning for Robotic Arm Control," 2018 Latin American Robotic Symposium, 2018 Brazilian Symposium on Robotics (SBR) and 2018 Workshop on Robotics in Education (WRE), João Pessoa, Brazil, 2018, pp. 357-362, doi: 10.1109/LARS/SBR/WRE.2018.00071.
- [4] Y. Zhang, Z. Lu, C. Wang, C. Liu and Y. Wang, "Voice control dual arm robot based on ROS system," 2018 IEEE International Conference on Intelligence and Safety for Robotics (ISR), Shenyang, China, 2018, pp. 232-237, doi: 10.1109/IISR.2018.8535942.
- [5] R. K. Megalingam, R. V. Rohith Raj, T. Akhil, A. Masetti, A. N. Chowdary and V. S. Naick, "Integration of Vision based Robot Manipulation using ROS for Assistive Applications," 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA), Coimbatore, India, 2020, pp. 163-169, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA48905.2020.9183013.
- [6] S. Tasnim, M. Z. Hasan, T. Ahmed, M. T. Hasan, F. J. Uddin and T. Farah, "A ROS-based Voice Controlled Robotic Arm for Automatic Segregation of Medical Waste Using YOLOv3," 2022 2nd International Conference on Computer, Control and Robotics (ICCCR), Shanghai, China, 2022, pp. 81-85, doi: 10.1109/ICCCR54399.2022.9790152.
- [7] A. Salim, A. C. R., P. Salprakash, and B. Thomas, "Voice controlled robotic arm," *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol. (IRJET)*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 2121–2124, Apr. 2017.
- [8] L. Jia, B. K. Styler, and N. Du, "More than automation: User insights into the functionality and interface of wheelchair-mounted robotic arms," in *Proc. 20th ACM/IEEE Int. Conf. Human-Robot Interaction (HRI)*, Melbourne, Australia, 2025, pp. 677–685. doi: 10.1109/HRI61500.2025.10974057.
- [9] K. Karan, A. Jirobe, R. Ingale, and S. S. Kale, "Voice control armed robot assistant using Arduino Uno," *Int. J. Innov. Sci. Res. Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 960–963, Mar. 2024. doi: 10.38124/ijisrt/IJISRT24MAR976.
- [10] J. Nannda, A. Chouhan, L. V. Dora, A. Verma, and T. Gupta, "A robotic arm vehicle using voice recognition for physically challenged people," in *Proc. 2nd Int. Conf. Adv. Comput., Commun. Inf. Technol. (ICAICCIT)*, 2024, pp. 858–864. doi: 10.1109/ICAICCIT64383.2024.10912202.
- [11] T. V. Abhiram and G. Udupa, Voice controlled 6 DoF arm mobile robot in an assisted home environment, preprint, *Research Square*, Nov. 6, 2024. doi: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-5332238/v1.
- [12] Y. Zhang, C. Chen, and C. Yang, "Task extension of robot with voice control based on dynamical movement primitives," in *Proc. Int. Symp. Autonomous Syst. (ISAS)*, 2020, pp. 82–89. doi: 10.1109/ISAS49493.2020.9378861.
- [13] R. S. Kanash, S. E. Alavi, and A. A. Abed, "Design and implementation of voice controlled robotic arm," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Commun. Inf. Technol. (ICICT)*, Basra, Iraq, 2021, pp. 284–289. doi: 10.1109/ICICT50921.2021.9397024.
- [14] S. Minera and K. George, "Voice controlled robotic arm with object detection as a feedback system for visually impaired individuals," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Comput. Eng. Technol. (ICCET)*, 2024, pp. 1–7. doi: 10.1109/ICCET2024.10961358.
- [15] M. Saravanan, J. S. Prasath, C. S. Karthik, A. Harish Ramanan, S. R. Balaji, and P. Naveen, "A voice-controlled robotic arm for material handling," in *Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Signal Process. Commun. (ICSPC)*, Coimbatore, India, 2023, pp. 382–387. doi: 10.1109/ICSPC57692.2023.10125875.
- [16] S. Kuriakose, H. M. M. Harshitha, D. G. Keerthana, S. Adarsh, and H. K. Harshitha, "Wireless voice controlled robot," in *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Adv. Comput. Commun. Syst. (ICACCS)*, 2023, pp. 189–194. doi: 10.1109/ICACCS57279.2023.1011

